

USAGE OF GEOGRIDS IN FLEXIBLE PAVEMENT DESIGN

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CERTIFICATE

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in partial fulfillment for the award of the Degree of Bachelor of Technology in Civil Engineering to the *Jawaharlal Nehru Technological University – Pulivendula* is a record of bonafide work carried out under my guidance and supervision.

The results embodied in this project report have not been submitted to any other University or Institute for the award of any Degree or Diploma.

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We hereby declare that this submission is our own work and that to best of our Knowledge and belief, it contains no material previously published or written by another person or material which has been accepted for the award of any degree or diploma of any Universities or institute of higher learning.

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Abstract

As on 31st March 2018, estimates the total road length in India 6,603,293km (4,103,096 mi) making the Indian road network, the second largest road network in the world after the united states. But the roads are not giving the desired result due to poor CBR value.

Roads in India have mostly the problems like the formation of potholes, ruts, cracks and localized depression and settlement, especially during rainy season. These are mainly due to the insufficient bearing capacity of the subgrade in water saturated condition. The subgrade soil mostly yields low CBR value 2-5%. In the CBR method of pavement design (IRC:37-2012) the total thickness of pavement increases exponentially with a decrease in the CBR value of subgrade soil which in turn increases the cost of construction. So, it has been tried to use the geogrid material for increasing the bearing capacity of the subgrade. Laboratory and simulated field CBR tests are conducted on soil samples with and without the inclusion of geogrid layer and also by varying the position of it in the mould. Use of geogrid increases the CBR value of the subgrade and thereby reduces the pavement thickness considerably up to 40%.

This study will have a positive impact on cost as it will reduce the Project as well as maintenance cost of the road. Our project will discuss in detail the process and its successful applications.

KEYWORDS: Geogrids, Reinforcement, CBR Value, Flexible Pavement, Subgrade, Highway, Design, Expansive Soil

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CHAPTER-1

1.1 INTRODUCTION

One of the major problems faced by the engineers in highway construction in plains and coastal areas of India is the presence of soft/ loose soil at ground level. Roads constructed over this loose soil demands higher thickness of granular materials resulting in the high cost of construction. Alternately attempts of reducing the thickness of pavement layer to make an economic construction will lead to early damage to the pavement which in turn will make the road unserviceable within a short period after construction. This condition may be further worsened if supplemented with poor drainage or lack of it. Some states of India is situated in a region of high rainfall area suffers from poor drainage as well as weak subgrade condition. This is one of the major causes of deplorable road condition in those states.

Looking at the poor road condition of some states of India use of geogrid is thought for road construction to improve the performance of roads. Geogrid a geosynthetic manufactured from polymers is selected for this purpose.

Geogrids used within a pavement system perform two of the primary functions of Geosynthetics: separation and reinforcements. Due to the large aperture size associated with most commercial geogrid products, geogrids are typically not used for achieving separation of dissimilar material. The ability of a geogrid to separate two materials is a function of the gradations of the two materials and is generally outside the specifications for typical pavement materials. However, geogrids can theoretically provide some measure of separation, albeit limited. For this reason, separation is a secondary function of geogrids used in pavements. The primary function of geogrids used pavements in reinforcement, in which the geogrid mechanically improves the engineering properties of the pavement system. The reinforcement mechanisms associated with geogrids.

1.2 OBJECTIVES OF THE PROJECT

- ✚ To reduce the thickness of Pavement. So, as to reduce the cost of road construction.
- ✚ To Design Pavement thickness based on CBR and msa traffic as per IRC:37-2012.
- ✚ To increase the load carrying capacity of the road (Strength of road).
- ✚ Increase the Service Life of Road

1.3 GEOSYNTHETICS, IT'S TYPES AND APPLICATIONS

Geosynthetics have been defined by the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) Committee D35 on geosynthetics as planar products manufactured from polymeric materials used with soil, rock, earth, or other geotechnical engineering related material as an integral part of a man-made project, structure or system. Geosynthetics is the term used to describe a range of polymeric products used for Civil Engineering construction works.

Geosynthetics are synthetic products used to stabilize terrain. They are generally polymeric products used to solve engineering problems.

This includes eight main product categories: geotextiles, geogrids, geonets, geomembranes, clay liners, geofilm, geocell and geocomposites. The polymeric nature of the products makes them suitable for use in the ground where high levels of durability are required. They can also be used in exposed applications. Geosynthetics are available in a wide range of forms and materials. These products have a wide range of applications and are currently used in many civil, geotechnical, transportation, geoenvironmental, hydraulic and private development applications including roads, airfields, railroads, embankments, retaining structures, reservoirs, canals, dams, erosion control, sediment control, landfill liners, landfill covers, mining, aquaculture, and agriculture.

Types of Geosynthetics:

Fig-1.1 Types of Geosynthetics

1.3.1 GENERAL APPLICATIONS OF GEOSYNTHETICS

Four of the most common general uses of geosynthetics for local agencies are:

1. Separation

One of the most common uses of geosynthetics is to use a geotextile to provide separation of two layers with different soil properties. Separation is the placement of a flexible geosynthetic material, like a porous geotextile, between dissimilar materials so that the integrity and functioning of both the materials can remain undisturbed or even improved. Using a road as an example, the separator will prevent the aggregate base course from sinking into weaker subgrade material (aggregate loss) and preventing fine material in the subgrade from pumping up into the aggregate base course (pumping). If

aggregate loss or pumping occurs, the strength of the pavement can be drastically reduced as shown in Plate 1 below which shows the reduced “effective” thickness of the aggregate base course.

a) Aggregate Loss due to lack of separation b) Separator prevents Aggregate Loss
Fig 1.2 - Geosynthetic Separator preventing Aggregate Loss (Kercher et.al)

2. Filtration

In this type of application, the geosynthetic acts as a filter by preventing material from washing out while allowing the water to flow through. The most common uses of this application are geotextiles which wrap around an edge drain, geotextiles placed under erosion control devices, and geotextiles used behind structures such as retaining walls.

Fig-1.3 Edge Drain wrapped with Geotextile (Kercher, et. al)

3. Drainage

Although filtering applications are commonly referred to as drainage applications, they are different. Drainage applications refer to situations where the water flows within

the plane of the geosynthetic product (in-plane drainage). In filtration applications, the water flows across the plane of the material.

Although certain types of geotextiles provide some in-plane drainage, most drainage situations require a geo-composite drainage product such as prefabricated sheet drains that provide a much greater drainage capacity.

4. Reinforcement

In this application, the structural stability of the soil is greatly improved by the tensile strength of the geosynthetic material. This concept is similar to that of reinforcing concrete with steel. Since concrete is weak in tension, reinforcing steel is used to strengthen it. Geosynthetic materials function in a similar manner as the reinforcing steel by providing tensile strength that helps to hold the soil in place. Reinforcement provided by geotextiles or geogrids allows embankments and roads to be built over very weak soils and allows for steeper embankments to be built.

Fig-1.4 Soil Reinforcement of an Embankment using a Geosynthetic (Kercher et.al)

Fig- 1.5 Earth Reinforced Retaining Wall using a Geosynthetic (Kercher et.al)

5. Barrier (Containment or Sealing)

The barrier or containment function involves the use of an impervious geosynthetic for situations where structures require a waterproofing membrane, or to function as a no-leak ground lining for liquid and solid waste disposal sites and the top capping seal. This function is best performed by a geomembrane. A non-woven geotextile performs this function when impregnated with asphalt or other polymeric mixes rendering it relatively impermeable to both cross-plane and in-plane flow. The classic application of geotextile as a liquid barrier is paved road rehabilitation. Here, the nonwoven geotextile is placed on the existing pavement surface following the application of an asphalt tack cloth. The geotextile absorbs asphalt to become a waterproofing membrane minimizing the vertical flow of water into the pavement structures. Other appropriate geosynthetics are geosynthetic clay liners and certain geocomposites.

6. Protection

The protection function relates to including a protective geosynthetic for strength or resistance to surrounding conditions as part of a geocomposite in a situation where the material used to provide a major function, for example, drainage, is vulnerable to conditions present in the surrounding environment. Some geosynthetic and natural barriers need to be protected against drainage

7. Erosion control

The erosion control function is concerned with the geosynthetics to hold surfaces in place and prevent erosion. Some geosynthetics permit protective vegetation to grow through the fabric so that a natural (rooted) resistance to erosion develops. The geosynthetic may be designed to gradually decompose or degrade.

Identification of the Usual Primary Function for Each Type of Geosynthetic

Type of Geosynthetic (GS)	Separation	Reinforcement	Filtration	Drainage	Containment
Geotextile (GT)	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Geogrid (GG)	✓	✓			
Geonet (GN)				✓	
Geomembrane (GM)					✓
Geosynthetic Clay Liner (GCL)					✓
Geopipe (GP)				✓	
Geofoam (GF)	✓				
Geocells (GL)		✓		✓	
Drainage cell (DC)		✓	✓	✓	
Geocomposite (GC)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table-1.1 Primary Function for Each Type of Geosynthetic.

1.4 GEOGRIDS AND IT'S TYPES

A Geo-Grid is a polymeric structure, unidirectional or bidirectional, in the form of a manufactured sheet, consisting of a regular network of integrally connected elements which may be linked by extrusion, bonding, and whose openings are larger than the constituents and are used in geotechnical, environmental, hydraulic and transportation engineering applications.

Geogrids are unitized woven yarns or bonded straps. Geogrids consist of heavy strands of plastic materials arranged as longitudinal and transverse elements to outline a uniformly distributed and relatively large and grid-like array of apertures in the resulting

sheet. These apertures allow direct contact between soil particles on either side of the sheet. (Bergado and Abuel-Naga, 2005)

According to Wikipedia, Geogrids represent a rapidly growing segment within geosynthetics. Rather than being a woven, nonwoven or knitted textile fabric, geogrids are polymers formed into a very open, grid-like configuration, i.e., they have large apertures between individual ribs in the machine and cross-machine directions. Geogrids are (a) either stretched in one or two directions for improved physical properties, (b) made on weaving or knitting machinery by standard textile manufacturing methods, or (c) by bonding rods or straps together. There are many specific application areas, however, they function almost exclusively as reinforcement materials. Modern geogrids were invented by Dr. Brian Mercer (Blackburn, UK) in the late 1970s. Dr. Mercer devised and patented the stretched sheet method of production which results in a stiff polymer grid and avoids the bonding of separate elements required in a woven or knitted grid. Subsequent development by Dr. Mercer led to the uniaxial (single direction stretch) geogrid with rectangular apertures and the biaxial (two-way stretch) geogrid with virtually square apertures.

Types of Geogrids

✚ *Based on the manufacturing process involved in geogrids it can be of*

- Extruded Geogrid
- Woven Geogrid
- Bonded Geogrid

✚ *Based on which direction the stretching is done during manufacture, geogrids are classified as*

- Uniaxial geogrids
- Biaxial Geogrids

Uniaxial Geogrids

These geogrids are formed by the stretching of ribs in the longitudinal direction. So, in this case, the material possesses high tensile strength in the longitudinal direction than on the transverse direction.

Biaxial Geogrids

Here during the punching of polymer sheets, the stretching is done in both directions. Hence the function of tensile strength is equally given to both transverse and longitudinal direction.

Types of Geogrids

1.5 APPLICATIONS OF GEOGRIDS

❖ **Confining the Aggregates**

The geogrids serve the function of holding or capturing the aggregates together. This method of interlocking the aggregates would help in an earthwork that is stabilized mechanically. The apertures in geogrids help in interlocking the aggregates or the soil that is placed over them. A representation of this concept is shown below.

Fig 1.7 Representation of Geogrid Confining the aggregates

The geogrids as mentioned above helps in redistribution of load over a wider area. This function has made the pavement construction more stabilized and strong. *It has the following functional mechanisms when applied for pavement construction:*

1. Tension Membrane Effect

This mechanism is based on the concept of vertical stress distribution. This vertical stress is from the deformed shape of the membrane as shown in the figure below. This mechanism was initially considered as the primary mechanism. But later studies proved the lateral restraining mechanism is the major criteria that must be taken into consideration.

Fig-1.8 Tension Member Effect

2. Improvement of Bearing Capacity

One of the main mechanism happening after Geogrid installation in pavement is the reduction in lateral movement of the aggregate. This would result in the elimination of stresses; that if exists would have moved to the subgrade.

The Geogrid layer possesses sufficient frictional resistance that opposes subgrade lateral movement. This mechanism hence improves the bearing capacity of the layer. Reduction of outward stresses means inward stresses are formed, which is the reason behind the increase in bearing capacity.

Fig- 1.9 Mechanism for Improved Bearing Capacity

3. Lateral Restraining Capability

The stresses produced by means of the wheel loadings coming over the pavement results in the lateral movement of the aggregates. Which in turn affects the stability of the whole pavement arrangement. The Geogrid act a restraint against this lateral movement.

Fig-1.10 *Lateral Restraining Capability*

1.6 CHARACTERISTICS OF EXPANSIVE SOIL

Expansive Soil is a kind of high plastic clay. Because it has a Strong hydrophilic mineral composition, its engineering prosperities embodies that its shape contracts under dehydrating, Inflation and softening under the influence of water and the strength attenuates. This is very difficult to construct in the region of expansive soil. In the region of seasonal frozen, as capillary water rising height is larger; it is prone to the phenomenon of frost boil or thawing settlement. It has important meaning to improve hydrophilic and physical and mechanical properties of expansive soil for Slope stability of embankment and cutting of highway engineering and reducing the cost of investment. The paper discusses the engineering properties of expansive soil in Detail; expound some main methods of improved expansive soil at home and abroad and compare and analysis the mechanism and characteristics of the corresponding methods. The paper introduces preliminary testing methods of Expansive soil performance and prospects improved in the future.

Expansive clay is a clay soil that is prone to large volume changes (swelling and shrinking) that are directly related to changes in water content. Soils with a high content of expansive minerals can form deep cracks in drier seasons or years; such soils are called vertisols. Soils with smectite clay minerals, including montmorillonite and bentonite, have the most dramatic shrink-swell capacity.

CHAPTER-2

LITERATURE REVIEW

States that the first use of fabrics in reinforcing roads was attempted by the South Carolina Highway Department in 1926. A heavy cotton fabric was placed on a primed earth base, hot asphalt was applied to the fabric, and a thin layer of sand was put on the asphalt. The department published the results of this work in 1935, describing eight separate field experiments until the fabric deteriorated, the results showed that the roads were in good condition and that the fabric reduced cracking, raveling, and localized road failures. This project was certainly the forerunner of the separation and reinforcement functions of geosynthetic materials as we know them today. There are specific types of geosynthetics: geotextiles, geogrids, geonets, geomembranes, geosynthetic-clay liners, geofoams, and geocomposites.

Geogrids consist of heavy strands of plastic materials arranged as longitudinal and transverse elements to outline a uniformly distributed and relatively large grid-like array of apertures in the resulting sheet. These apertures allow direct contact between soil particles on either side of the sheet. Geogrids are characterized by integrally connected elements within-plane apertures (openings) uniformly distributed between the elements. The apertures allow the soil to fill the space between the elements, thereby increasing soil interaction with the geogrid and ensuring unrestricted vertical drainage. Their applications are not only in highway but also in railroad track construction and rehabilitation.

Geogrids have been used successfully in pavement layer studies; placed geogrid between gravel base course and sand subgrade and showed the increase in CBR value of the subgrade material. **Gosavi et al** also investigated the strength behavior of soils reinforced with mixed geogrid woven fabric and showed that the soaked CBR without the geogrid was about 4.9% and after application of the geogrid test results showed an improvement in the CBR value. Naeini and Moayed indicated that using a geogrid at top of the layer 3 in a soil sample with different plasticity index causes a considerable increase in the CBR value compared with unreinforced soil in both soaked and unsoaked conditions. In order to quantify the amount of increase in the penetration resistance, the reinforcement ratio is taken into consideration. The reinforcement ratio according to is defined as the ratio of the Load with the geotextile to the Load without the geotextile.

Over the last three decades, the use of geosynthetics has recorded a tremendous increase in civil engineering constructions. This is a result of continuous research in laboratory and field all over the globe.

Giroud and Noirway (1982) after an extensive study developed design chart of unpaved pavement for using geosynthetic at the interface of the base layer and Subgrade soil. **Ramaswamy and Aziz** (1989) did an experimental investigation on the behavior of jute reinforced subgrade soil under dynamic load.

Mehndiratta et al 1993 and Patel, 1990 have reported that standard mould of diameter equal to 3 times the plunger diameter is found to be inadequate for determination of CBR value as the small size mould will provide additional confinement to geotextile. Therefore, the diameter of the mould is increased to 5 times the plunger diameter. Also, to determine the effect of lateral confinement on CBR value of reinforced soil, mould-plunger diameter ratio (D/d) is varied from 2 to 5 while the vertical pressure (surcharge), the thickness of the specimen, method of compaction is kept the same as the standard test.

Mehndiratta et al (2005) conducted CBR and plate load test on unreinforced and geotextile reinforced subgrade. It was observed that the increase in elastic moduli of coir reinforced layer when coir is replaced by synthetic geosynthetic geotextiles are only 5 percent. They also investigated the durability of coir by accelerating its degradability It was observed that phenol treated coir extends the life of coir. **Rao** (2007) has published a compilation of his work on geosynthetics and state of the art developments.

Babu et al, 2008 has developed a design methodology using IRC guidelines for the design of coir geotextiles reinforced road on the basis of laboratory experiment data and mathematical formulations.

CHAPTER-3

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 EXPENSIVE SOIL

Expansive soil is a kind of special Cohesive soil. the kind of soil can significantly become to soften after it absorbs water, and it also can become to contract after it losses water. It is a kind of Strong hydrophilic mineral geological body that was formed in the process of long-term natural geological historical role.

Expansive soil is high plastic clay that contains montmorillonite and illite as the main mineral composition. The clay content of the expansive soil is high, the free expansion rate is commonly more than 40%, and the liquid limit is higher than 40%. The expansive soil has not only the commonness of clay soil but also has its own particularity. The expansive soil has a specialty that it can be repeated deformation of wet bilge and drying shrinkage.

The engineering properties of expansive soil have multiple fractures, over consolidation, swelling, collapse, weathering properties, the intensity attenuation, etc. Swell-shrink of expansive soil caused the destruction of buildings because of having repeatability and long-term potential hazards for many times, often can cause disasters to human beings.

3.2 GEOGRID

Fig 3.1 GEOGRID

- ✚ Ease of Construction: The Geogrid can be installed in any weather conditions. This makes it more demanding.
- ✚ Land Optimization: This method of Geogrid installation in soils makes an unsuitable area suitable for preparing it to meet desired properties for construction. Geogrid thus helps in proper land utilization.
- ✚ Geogrid promotes soil stabilization.
- ✚ A higher strength soil mass is obtained.
- ✚ Higher load bearing capacity.
- ✚ It is a good remedy to retain soil from erosion
- ✚ No requirement of mortar. The material is implemented dry.
- ✚ No difficulty in material availability.
- ✚ Geogrids are flexible in nature. They are known for their versatility.
- ✚ Geogrids have high durability reducing maintenance cost. They are highly resistant to environmental influences.
- ✚ Materials are tested based on standard codes and regulations.

The Geogrid construction in pavement construction have following features

- ❖ **Improvement of subgrade:** The subgrade, which is the most important load-bearing strata, is made solid and strong by the Geogrids. The problem of soft subgrade can be solved by this method.
- ❖ **Reinforcement of pavement base:** The thickness of base if increased would increase the stiffness of base. But increasing thickness enormously is not economical. The reinforcement of a given base layer would give adequate stiffening that helps in reduction of thickness and time of construction. This also helps in increasing the life of the pavement.

3.3 METHODOLOGY

Laboratory and simulated field CBR tests are conducted on soil samples with and without the inclusion of Geo-grid and also by varying the position of it in the mould.

Fig 3.2 Methodology of Project

3.4 INSTALLATION OF PAVING GEOGRID

Roll Placement

Successful use of geosynthetics in pavements requires proper installation, and Figure shows the proper sequence of construction. Even though the installation techniques appear fairly simple, most geosynthetic problems in roadways occur as the result of improper construction techniques. If the geosynthetic is ripped or punctured during construction activities, it will not likely perform as desired. If a geogrid is placed with a lot of wrinkles or folds, it will not be in tension, and, therefore, cannot provide a reinforcing effect. Other problems occur due to insufficient cover over the geotextiles or geogrids, rutting of the subgrade prior to placing the geosynthetic, and thick lifts that exceed the bearing capacity of the soil. The following step-by-step procedures should be followed, along with careful observations of all construction activities.

1. The site should be cleared, grubbed, and excavated to design grade, stripping all topsoil, soft soils, or any other unsuitable materials. If moderate site conditions exist, i.e., CBR greater than 1, lightweight proof rolling operations should be considered to help locate unsuitable materials. Isolated pockets where additional excavation is required should be backfilled to promote positive drainage. Optionally, geotextile wrapped trench drains could be used to drain isolated areas.

Fig -3.3 PREPARE THE GROUND

Fig- 3.4 UNROLL THE GEOSYNTHETIC

Fig - 3.5 BACK DUMP AGGREGATE

Fig-3.6 SPREAD THE AGGREGATE

FIG-3.7 COMPACT THE AGGREGATE

2. During stripping operations, care should be taken not to excessively disturb the subgrade. This may require the use of lightweight dozers or grade-all's for low strength, saturated, noncohesive and low-cohesive soils. For extremely soft ground, such as peat bog areas, do not excavate surface materials so you may take advantage of the root mat strength if it exists. In this case, all vegetation should be cut at the

ground surface. Sawdust or sand can be placed over stumps or roots that extend above the ground surface to cushion the geogrid. Remember, the subgrade preparation must correspond to the survivability properties of either the geogrid.

3. Once the subgrade along a particular segment of the road alignment has been prepared, the geogrid should be rolled in line with the placement of the new roadway aggregate. Field operations can be expedited if the geogrid is manufactured to design widths in the factory so it can be unrolled in one continuous sheet. Geogrids should be placed directly on top of geotextiles when used together. The geosynthetic should not be dragged across the subgrade. The entire roll should be placed and rolled out as smoothly as possible. Wrinkles and folds in the geogrid should be removed by stretching and staking as required.
4. Parallel rolls of geotextiles or geogrids should be overlapped, sewn, or joined as required.
5. For curves, the geogrid should be cut and overlapped in the direction of the turn.
6. When the geogrid intersects an existing pavement area, the geosynthetic should extend to the edge of the old system. For widening or intersecting existing roads where geotextiles or geogrids have been used, consider anchoring the geogrid at the roadway edge. Ideally, the edge of the roadway should be excavated down to the existing geosynthetic and the existing geosynthetic mechanically connected to the new geosynthetic (i.e., mechanically connected with plastic ties to the geogrid). Overlaps, staples, and pins could also be utilized.
7. Before covering, the condition of the geogrid should be checked for excessive damage (i.e., holes, rips, tears, etc.) by an inspector experienced in the use of these materials. If excessive defects are observed, the section of the geosynthetic containing the defect should be repaired by placing a new layer of geosynthetic over the damaged area. The minimum required overlap required for parallel rolls should extend beyond the defect in all directions. Alternatively, the defective section can be replaced.
8. The base aggregate should be end-dumped on the previously placed aggregate. For very soft subgrades, pile heights should be limited to prevent possible subgrade failure. The maximum placement lift thickness for such soils should not exceed the design thickness of the road.

- 9.** The first lift of aggregate should be spread and graded to 12 in. (300 mm), or to the design thickness if less than 12 in. (300 mm), prior to compaction. At no time should traffic be allowed on a soft roadway with less than 8 in. (200 mm), (or 6 in. {150 mm} for $\text{CBR} \geq 3$) of aggregate over the geogrid. Equipment can operate on the roadway without aggregate for geocomposite installation under permeable bases if the subgrade is of sufficient strength. For extremely soft soils, lightweight construction vehicles will likely be required for access on the first lift. Construction vehicles should be limited in size and weight so rutting in the initial lift is limited to 3 in. (75 mm). If rut depths exceed 3 in. (75 mm), it will be necessary to decrease the construction vehicle size and/or weight or to increase the lift thickness. For example, it may be necessary to reduce the size of the dozer required to blade out the fill or to deliver the fill-in half-loaded rather than fully loaded trucks.
- 10.** The first lift of base aggregate should be compacted by tracking with the dozer, then compacted with a smooth-drum vibratory roller to obtain a minimum compacted density. For the construction of permeable bases, compaction shall meet specification requirements. For very soft soils, design density should not be anticipated for the first lift and, in this case, compaction requirements should be reduced. One recommendation is to allow compaction of 5% less than the required minimum specification density for the first lift.
- 11.** Construction should be performed parallel to the road alignment. Turning should not be permitted on the first lift of base aggregate. Turn-outs may be constructed at the roadway edge to facilitate construction.
- 12.** On very soft subgrades, if the geogrid is to provide some reinforcing, pretensioning of the geosynthetic should be considered. For pretensioning, the area should be proof rolled by a heavily loaded, rubber-tired vehicle such as a loaded dump truck. The wheel load should be equivalent to the maximum expected for the site. The vehicle should make at least four passes over the first lift in each area of the site. Alternatively, once the design aggregate has been placed, the roadway could be used for a time prior to paving to prestress the geogrid-aggregate system in key areas.

CHAPTER-4

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAMME

4.1 TRAFFIC DATA COLLECTION

SL: NO	Timings:	HCV	MCV	LCV	TWO WHEELERS	CYCLES	Total
1	8:00 am - 9:00 am	76	11	212	518	5	822
2	9:00 am - 10:00 am	56	15	176	542	1	790
3	10:00 am - 11:00 am	41	15	183	492	1	732
4	11:00 am - 12:00 pm	45	10	160	459	1	675
5	12:00 pm - 1:00 pm	37	8	151	414	3	613
6	1:00 pm - 2:00 pm	52	12	146	355	3	568
7	2:00 pm - 3:00 pm	43	16	116	291	4	470
8	3:00 pm - 4:00 pm	49	5	119	279	2	454
9	4:00 pm - 5:00 pm	51	12	177	407	1	648
10	5:00 pm - 6:00 pm	75	11	142	311	2	541
11	6:00 pm - 7:00 pm	56	23	124	330	0	533
12	7:00 pm - 8:00 pm	68	4	149	289	0	510
Total		649	142	1855	4687	23	7356

Table-4.1 Traffic Data Observables

$P = HCV + MCV + LCV = 2646$

Graph -4.1 Traffic Data Variation with Time

4.2 GRAIN SIZE DISTRIBUTION

IS: 2720 (Part 4) – 1985 – Method of test for soil (Part 4-Grain size analysis)

AIM:

To determine the effective size and the uniformity coefficient of a given sample of soil and to classify.

Equipment for Particle Size Distribution:

1. Set of fine sieves, 2mm, 1mm, 600 micron, 425, 212, 150, and 75 micron.
2. Set of coarse sieves, 100mm, 80mm, 40mm, 10mm, and 4.75mm.
3. Weighing balance with an accuracy of 0.1% of the mass of the sample.
4. Oven
5. Mechanical shaker
6. Trays
7. Mortar with a rubber covered pestle.
8. Brushes
9. Riffler

Fig-4.1 Set of Sieves

THEORY

The size of the individual grain is an important factor governing soil behavior and therefore, the most common soil test is the grain size analysis. The result can be represented by the numerical values and indicate some characteristic grain size and degree of uniformity. Allen Hazen, after performing a number of tests with filter materials concluded that in the loose state the permeability of the soil depends on “effective size” and “uniformity coefficient”

The effective size is defined as the size of material corresponding to 10% finer on the grain size distribution curve denoted by D_{10} . This means 10% of the particles are fine and 90% are coarser than the effective size.

The uniformity coefficient is the ratio of D_{60} to D_{10} . It gives the measure of grading of the soil. A high uniformity coefficient means a low degree of uniformity or well – graded material. If uniformity coefficient is less than 4, the soil is uniform or poorly graded.

Uniformity coefficient is between 5 and 9 the soil is medium graded. Uniformity coefficient is more than 10, the soil is well graded.

PROCEDURE:

1. Arrange the sieve of sizes 4.75 mm, 2.36 mm, 1.18 mm, 600 μ , 425 μ , 300 μ , 150 μ and 75 μ in the order of decreasing aperture size, after ensuring that all of them are clean. The receiver is placed at the bottom.
2. Weight about 1000 gms, of the given sample of soil and, pour it into the topmost sieve. The lid is kept in position.
3. Shake the sieves for about 15 minutes holding the sieves inclined at an angle of 15° to the vertical. The shaking is done in a circular motion.
4. Determine the weight of soil particles retained on each sieve and tabulated the results.
5. Draw the grain – size distribution curve with the logarithm of the aperture size on X-axis, and percentage passing through the sieve on Y – axis. Fit in a smooth curve and determine the value of D_{10} , D_{30} , and D_{60} .
6. Calculate the value of uniformity coefficient C_u and the coefficient of curvature C_c .

4.3 ATTERBERG LIMITS

The Atterberg limits are a basic measure of the critical water contents of a fine-grained soil: its shrinkage limit, plastic limit, and liquid limit.

Depending on the water content of the soil, it may appear in four states: solid, semi-solid, plastic and liquid. In each state, the consistency and behavior of a soil are different and consequently so are its engineering properties. Thus, the boundary between each state can be defined based on a change in the soil's behavior. The Atterberg limits can be used to distinguish between silt and clay, and to distinguish between different types of silts and clays.

4.3.1 LIQUID LIMIT

IS 2720(Part 5)-1985- Methods of test for soils: Determination of liquid and plastic limit.

The liquid limit (LL) is conceptually defined as the water content at which the behavior of clayey soil changes from plastic to liquid. However, the transition from

plastic to liquid behavior is gradual over a range of water contents, and the shear strength of the soil is not actually zero at the liquid limit. The precise definition of the liquid limit is based on standard test procedures described below.

Aim:

To determine the liquid limit of the Soil Sample using Casagrande apparatus.

APPARATUS:

- Liquid limit device (casagrande apparatus).
- Standard grooving tool
- Balance
- Hot air oven
- Containers for moisture determination
- Graduated jar

PREPARATION OF SAMPLE:

After receiving the soil sample it is dried in air or in the oven (maintained at a temperature of 60⁰C). If clods are there in soil sample then it is broken with the help of wooden mallet. The soil passing 425-micron sieve is used in this test.

PROCEDURE:

1. About 120 gm. of air-dried soil from a thoroughly mixed portion of material passing 425 microns IS sieve is obtained.
2. Distilled water is mixed to the soil thus obtained in a mixing disc to form a uniform paste. The paste shall have a consistency that would require 30 to 35 drops of the cup to cause closure of the standard groove for sufficient length.
3. A portion of the paste is placed in the cup of Casagrande device and spread into the portion with few strokes of a spatula.
4. It is trimmed to a depth of 1 cm. at the point of maximum thickness and excess of soil is returned to the dish.
5. The soil in the cup is divided by the firm strokes of the grooving tool along the diameter through the center line of the follower so that clean sharp groove of proper dimension is formed.

6. Then the cup is dropped by turning crank at the rate of two revolutions per second until two halves of the soil cake come in contact with each other for a length of about 12 mm. by flow only.
7. The number of blows required to cause the groove close for about 12 mm. is recorded.
8. A representative portion of soil is taken from the cup for water content determination.
9. The test is repeated with different moisture contents at least 3 times for blows between 10 and 40.

Fig-4.2 Casagrande Apparatus

SAFETY & PRECAUTIONS:

- ✓ Soil used for liquid limit determination should not be oven dried prior to testing.
- ✓ In LL test the groove should be closed by the flow of soil and not by slippage between the soil and the cup
- ✓ After mixing the water to the soil sample, sufficient time should be given to permeate the water throughout out the soil mass
- ✓ Wet soil taken in the container for moisture content determination should not be left open in the air, the container with soil sample should either be placed in desiccators or immediately be weighed.

4.3.2 PLASTIC LIMIT

IS 2720(Part 5)-1985- Methods of test for soils: Determination of liquid and plastic limit.

PLASTIC LIMIT: The Plastic limit is the water content corresponding to an arbitrary limit between the plastic and semi-solid states of consistency of a soil. It is defined as the minimum water content at which a soil will just begin to crumble when rolled into a thread approximately 3 mm in diameter.

AIM:

To determine the plastic limit of the soil.

EQUIPMENT & APPARATUS:

- Oven
- Balance (0.01 g accuracy)
- Sieve [425 microns]
- Flat glass surface for rolling

PREPARATION SAMPLE:

After receiving the soil sample it is dried in air or in the oven (maintained at a temperature of 60⁰C). If clods are there in soil sample then it is broken with the help of wooden mallet. The soil passing 425-micron sieve is used in this test.

PROCEDURE:

1. A soil sample of 20 gm. passing 425 microns IS sieve is to be taken.
2. It is to be mixed with distilled water thoroughly in the evaporating dish till the soil mass becomes plastic enough to be easily moulded with fingers.
3. It is to be allowed to season for sufficient time, to allow water to permeate throughout the soil mass.
4. 10 gms. of the above plastic mass is to be taken and is to be rolled between fingers and glass plate with just sufficient pressure to roll the mass into a thread of uniform diameter throughout its length. The rate of rolling shall be between 60 and 90 stokes per minute.
5. The rolling is to be continued till the thread becomes 3 mm. in diameter.
6. The soil is then kneaded together to a uniform mass and rolled again.
7. The process is to be continued until the thread crumbled with the diameter of 3 mm.
8. The pieces of the crumbled thread are to be collected in an airtight container for moisture content determination.

Fig – 4.3 Plastic Limit Test Apparatus

Fig – 4.4 Plastic Limit Test

SAFETY & PRECAUTIONS:

- Soil used for plastic limit determination should not be oven dried prior to testing.
- After mixing the water to the soil sample, sufficient time should be given to permeate the water throughout out the soil mass
- Wet soil taken in the container for moisture content determination should not be left open in the air, the container with soil sample should either be placed in desiccators or immediately be weighed.

4.4 STANDARD PROCTOR COMPACTION TEST

IS 2720(Part 7)-1980- Methods of test for soils: Determination of water content-dry density relation using light compaction.

OBJECTIVE:

For determination of the relation between the water content and the dry density of soils using light compaction.

EQUIPMENTS & APPARATUS:

- Cylindrical mould & accessories [volume = 1000cm³]
- Rammer [2.6 kg]
- Balance [1g accuracy]
- Sieves [19mm]
- Mixing tray
- Trowel
- Graduated cylinder [500 ml capacity]
- Metal container

Fig- 4.5 Standard Proctor Test

PREPARATION OF SAMPLE:

Obtain a sufficient quantity (10 kg) of air-dried soil and pulverize it. Take about 5 kg of soil passing through 19mm sieve in a mixing tray.

PROCEDURE:

1. 5 Kg. of soil is taken and the water is added to it to bring its moisture content to about 4 % in coarse-grained soils and 8% in case of fine-grained soils with the help of graduated cylinder
2. The mould with base plate attached is weighed to the nearest 1 gm (M_1). The extension collar is to be attached to the mould.
3. Then the moist soil in the mould is compacted in three equal layers, each layer being given 25 blows from the 2.6 Kg rammer dropped from a height of 310 mm. above the soil.
4. The extension is removed and the compacted soil is leveled off carefully to the top of the mould by means of a straight edge.
5. Then the mould and soil are weighed to the nearest 1 gm. (M_2).
6. The soil is removed from the mould and a representative soil sample is obtained water content determination.
7. Steps 3 to 6 are repeated after adding a suitable amount of water to the soil in an increasing order.

SAFETY & PRECAUTIONS:

- Use hand gloves & safety shoes while compacting.
- Adequate period (about 15 minutes for clayey soils and 56 minutes for coarse-grained soils) is allowed after mixing the water and before compacting into the mould.
- The blows should be uniformly distributed over the surface of each layer.

4.5 TENSILE TEST OF GEOGRID

TESTING OF SECUGRID 40/40 Q1 FOR ITS TENSILE TEST:

INTRODUCTION: The Secugrid 40/40 Q1 was used in the construction of Bapatla pedanandipadu R&B road Narasayapalem in Bapatla mandal as a part of its maintenance work. In this connection, the geogrid test specimen was sent to the soil mechanics laboratory of NIT Warangal to test it for its tensile strength.

Laboratory Testing: The supplied secugrid 40/40 Q1 was tested for its tensile strength as per ASTM D 6637-01.

Test Result: The test results are presented in table 1

Sl. No	Specimen Number	Max. Tensile strength (KN/m)	Percent Elongation @ 40 (KN/m)
1	Specimen 1	41.86	7.86
2	Specimen 2	47.06	8.00
3	Specimen 3	40.02	7.93

Table-4.3 Secugrid 40/40 Q1 Test Result

Graph-4.2 Load Vs Displacement Plot for Secugrid 40/40 Q1

INFERENCE: The tensile strength tests were carried out on the single rib and the strength is calculated per meter width and presented in table 1. The test results as presented above can be compared with the standard values for the Secugrid 40/40 Q1 by the Concerned Department.

4.6 CALIFORNIA BEARING RATIO TEST

IS: 2720(Part 16)-1973- Methods of test for soils: Laboratory determination of CBR

OBJECTIVE:

Determination of CBR of soil either in undisturbed or Remoulded condition.

EQUIPMENT / APPARATUS:

- Compression machine
- Proving ring, Dial gauge, Timer
- Sampling tube
- Split mould
- Vernier caliper, Balance

PREPARATION SAMPLE:

The test may be performed

- (a) On undisturbed soil specimen
- (b) On remoulded soil specimen

(a) On undisturbed specimen

The undisturbed specimen is obtained by fitting to the mould, the steel cutting edge of 150 mm internal diameter and pushing the mould as gently as possible into the ground. When the mould is sufficiently full of soil, it shall be removed by under digging. The top and bottom surfaces are then trimmed flat so as to give the required length of the specimen.

(b) On remoulded Specimens

The dry density for remoulding should be either the field density or if the subgrade is to be compacted, at the maximum dry density value obtained from the Proctor Compaction test. If it is proposed to carry out the CBR test on an unsoaked specimen, the moisture content for remoulding should be the same as the equilibrium moisture content which the soil is likely to reach subsequent to the construction of the road. If it is proposed to carry

Fig-4.6 California Bearing Ratio Test

out the CBR test on a soaked specimen, the moisture content for remoulding should be at the optimum and soaked under water for 96 hours.

Soil Sample – The material used in the remoulded specimen should all pass through a 19 mm IS sieve. Allowance for the larger material may be made by replacing it with an equal amount of material which passes a 19 mm sieve but is retained on a 4.75 mm IS sieve. This procedure is not satisfactory if the size of the soil particles is predominantly greater than 19 mm. The specimen may be compacted statically or dynamically.

I. Compaction by Static Method

The mass of the wet soil at the required moisture content to give the desired density when occupying the standard specimen volume in the mould is calculated. A batch of soil is thoroughly mixed with water to give the required water content. The correct mass of the moist soil is placed in the mould and compaction obtained by pressing in displacer disc, a filter paper is placed between the disc & soil.

II. Compaction by Dynamic Method

For dynamic compaction, a representative sample of soil weighing approximately 4.5 kg or more for fine grained soils and 5.5 kg or more for granular soil shall be taken and mixed thoroughly with water. If the soil is to be compacted to the maximum dry density at the optimum water content determined in accordance with light compaction or heavy compaction, the exact mass of soil required is to be taken and the necessary quantity of water added so that the water content of soil sample is equal to the determined optimum water content. The mould with extension collar attached is clamped to the base plate. The spacer disc is inserted over the base plate and a disc of coarse filter paper placed on the top of the spacer disc. The soil water mixture is compacted into the mould in accordance with the methods specified in light compaction test or heavy compaction test.

PROCEDURE:

1. The mould containing the specimen with the base plate in position but the top face exposed is placed on the lower plate of the testing machine.
2. Surcharge weights, sufficient to produce an intensity of loading equal to the weight of the base material and pavement is placed on the specimen.

3. To prevent upheaval of soil into the hole of the surcharge weights, 2.5 kg annular weight is placed on the soil surface prior to seating the penetration plunger after which the remainder of the surcharge weight is placed.
4. The plunger is to be seated under a load of 4 kg so that full contact is established between the surface of the specimen and the plunger.
5. The stress and strain gauges are then set to zero. The load is applied to the penetration plunger so that the penetration is approximately 1.25 mm per minute.
6. Readings of the load are taken at penetrations of 0.0, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 4.0, 5.0, 7.5, 10.0 and 12.5 mm.
7. The plunger is then raised and the mould detached from the loading equipment.

COMPUTATION:

Load-Penetration curve:

The load penetration curve is plotted taking penetration value on x-axis and Load values on Y-axis. Corresponding to the penetration value at which the CBR is desired, the corrected load value is taken from the load-penetration curve and the CBR calculated as follows

$$\text{California bearing ratio} = (P_T/P_S) \times 100$$

Where

P_T = Corrected unit (or total) test load corresponding to the chosen penetration curve, and

P_S = Unit(or total) standard load for the same depth of penetration as for P_S taken from standard code.

REPORT

The CBR values are usually calculated for penetration of 2.5 mm and 5 mm. The CBR value is reported to correct to the first decimal place.

SAFETY & PRECAUTIONS:

- Clean the sieves with the help of a brush, after sieving
- While weighing put the sieve with soil sample on the balance in a concentric position.
- Check the electric connection of the sieve shaker before conducting the test.

CHAPTER:5

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 TRAFFIC DATA ANALYSIS

Computation of Design Traffic:

$$\diamond N = \frac{365 * [(1+r)^n - 1] * A * D * F}{r}$$

Where,

- + N = Cumulative number of standard axles to be catered for in the design in terms of msa.
- + A=Initial traffic in the year of completion of construction in terms of the number of Commercial Vehicles Per Day (CVPD).
- + D = Lane distribution factor = **0.5**
- + F = Vehicle Damage Factor (VDF) = **3.5**
- + n = Design life in years = **15**
- + r = Annual growth rate of commercial vehicles in decimal = **7.5%**
- ◇ The traffic in the year of completion is estimated using the following formula $A = P (1 + r)^x$.

Where,

- + P= Number of commercial vehicles as per last count = **2646**
- + x = Number of years between the last count and the year of completion of construction. (say **1 Year**).
- ✓ By substituting above Values, **N Value** is Computed as **47.45 msa**.

5.2 GRAIN SIZE DISTRIBUTION

Sample Weight:1000 Grams

IS Sieve No (mm)	Wt. of Soil Retained in Grams	%Wt. Retained	Cumulative %Wt. retained	% finer
4.75	81.80	8.18	8.18	91.82
2.36	65.51	6.55	14.73	85.27
1.18	260.39	26.04	40.77	59.23
0.6	390.00	39.00	79.77	20.23
0.425	0.22	0.02	79.79	20.21
0.3	4.27	0.43	80.22	19.78
0.15	136.82	13.68	93.90	6.10
0.075	34.75	3.48	97.38	2.62
Pan	26.24	2.62	100.00	0.00

Table-5.1 Grain Size Distribution Data

Percentage Fines (Size Less than 75μ) < 5%

From Graph:

$$C_u = \frac{D_{60}}{D_{10}} = \frac{1.4}{0.18} = 7.78$$

$D_{10} = 0.18$

$D_{30} = 0.74$

$$C_c = \frac{D_{30}^2}{D_{60} \cdot D_{10}} = \frac{0.74^2}{1.4 \cdot 0.18} = 2.17$$

$D_{60} = 1.4$

i.e., %age Finer < 5, $C_u > 4$ & $C_c \approx 1 - 3$ then as per IS :1498 the Soil is **Well Graded Gravel**

5.3 ATTERBERG LIMITS

I. LIQUID LIMIT

SL.NO	DESCRIPTION	I	II	III
1	Number of Blows	13	26	36
2	Container Number	1	2	3
3	The weight of container + Wet Soil in grams	10.69	11.39	8.27
4	The weight of container +Dry Soil in grams	6.95	7.48	5.48
5	The weight of Water in grams	3.74	3.91	2.79
6	The weight of Dry Soil in grams	6.95	7.48	5.48
7	Water Content (w_L) in Percentages	53.81	52.27	50.91

Table-5.2 Liquid Limit Data of Soil Sample

From Graph:
Liquid Limit $w_L=52.17$

II. PLASTIC LIMIT

SL.NO	DESCRIPTION	I	II
1	Container Number	1	2
2	The weight of container + Wet Soil in grams	2.1	1.17
3	The weight of container +Dry Soil in grams	1.77	0.99
4	The weight of Water in grams	0.33	0.18
5	The weight of Dry Soil in grams	1.76	0.97
6	Water Content (w_P) in Percentages	18.75	18.56
7	Average Plastic Limit W_P	18.65	

Table-5.3 Plastic Limit Data of soil Sample

i.e., Plasticity index I_P : Liquid Limit – Plastic Limit: 33.52

$I_P > 17.$, High Plastic Soil

5.4 STANDARD PROCTOR COMPACTION TEST

The weight of the Mould: 4260 grams, Volume of the Mould: 1000 cc

SL NO:	DESCRIPTION	I	II	III	IV	V
1	The weight of mould + Wet soil in W_2 in grams	6170	6310	6340	6300	6260
2	The weight of Wet Soil (W_2-W_1) in grams	1910	2050	2080	2040	2000
3	Moisture Content Container Number	1	2	3	4	5
4	Weight of Container +Wet Soil in grams	70.65	91.90	152.08	111.78	134.85
5	Weight of Container + Dry Soil in grams	62.46	79.51	129.82	93.89	111.70
6	Weight of Water (4-5) in grams	8.19	12.39	22.26	17.89	23.15
7	Weight of Dry soil in grams	62.46	79.51	129.82	93.89	111.70
8	Water Content $w=6/7*100$	13.11	15.58	17.15	19.05	20.73
9	Bulk Density	1.91	2.05	2.08	2.04	2.00
10	Dry Density	1.69	1.77	1.78	1.71	1.66

Table-5.3 Standard Proctor Compaction Test Observables

Where., Bulk Density = $\frac{\text{Weight of wet soil}}{\text{Volume of the Mould}}$, , Dry Density = $\frac{\text{Bulk Density}}{1+\text{Water Content}}$

From Graph:

OMC (Optimum Moisture Content) : 16.65

MDD (Maximum Dry Density) : 1.784

5.5 CALIFORNIA BEARING RATIO TEST

I. WITHOUT GEOGRID

SL No:	Penetration in mm (C ₁)	Proving Ring Readings (C ₂) KN	Proving Ring Readings in division (C ₃ =C ₂ *5)	Load in Kg C ₄ =C ₃ *0.915
1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
2	0.5	3.0	15.0	13.7
3	1.0	3.8	19.0	17.4
4	1.5	4.2	21.0	19.2
5	2.0	4.8	24.0	22.0
6	2.5	5.0	25.0	22.9
7	4.0	5.5	27.5	25.2
8	5.0	5.8	29.0	26.5
9	7.5	6.5	32.5	29.7
10	10.0	6.7	33.5	30.7
11	12.5	7.1	35.5	32.5

Table-5.4 CBR Test Data Without Geogrid

Fig-5.1 Soil Sample without Geogrid

CBR @ 2.5 mm Penetration :1.67 , CBR @ 5.0 mm Penetration:1.36

II. WITH GEOGRID AT H/4 FROM THE BOTTOM

SL No:	Penetration in mm (C ₁)	Proving Ring Readings (C ₂) KN	Proving Ring Readings in division (C ₃ =C ₂ *5)	Load in Kg C ₄ =C ₃ *0.915
1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
2	0.5	2.5	12.5	11.4
3	1.0	3.2	16.0	14.6
4	1.5	3.7	18.5	16.9
5	2.0	4.7	23.5	21.5
6	2.5	5.4	27.0	24.7
7	4.0	5.7	28.5	26.1
8	5.0	6.1	30.5	27.9
9	7.5	6.3	31.5	28.8
10	10.0	6.8	34.0	31.1
11	12.5	7.0	35.0	32.0

Table-5.5 CBR Test Data with geogrid @ H/4 from bottom

Fig-5.2 Laboratory Experiment with Geogrid in CBR Mould

Graph-5.5 CBR Test With geogrid @ H/4 from bottom

CBR @ 2.5 mm Penetration :1.80, CBR @ 5.0 mm Penetration:1.29

III. WITH GEOGRID AT H/2 DISTANCE FROM THE BOTTOM

SL No:	Penetration in mm (C ₁)	Proving Ring Readings (C ₂) KN	Proving Ring Readings in division (C ₃ =C ₂ *5)	Load in Kg C ₄ =C ₃ *0.915
1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
2	0.5	3.7	18.5	16.9
3	1.0	4.9	24.5	22.4
4	1.5	5.6	28.0	25.6
5	2.0	6.7	33.5	30.7
6	2.5	7.5	37.5	34.3
7	4.0	7.7	38.5	35.2
8	5.0	8.1	40.5	37.1
9	7.5	8.5	42.5	38.9
10	10.0	9.2	46.0	42.1
11	12.5	9.5	47.5	43.5

Table-5.6 CBR Test Data with Geogrid @ H/2 from bottom

Fig-5.3 Tests Conducted in Laboratory

CBR @ 2.5 mm Penetration :2.50, CBR @ 5.0 mm Penetration : 2.74

IV. WITH GEOGRID AT 3H/4 DISTANCE FROM THE BOTTOM

SL No:	Penetration in mm (C ₁)	Proving Ring Readings (C ₂) KN	Proving Ring Readings in division (C ₃ =C ₂ *5)	Load in Kg C ₄ =C ₃ *0.915
1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
2	0.5	7.9	39.5	36.1
3	1.0	9.1	45.5	41.6
4	1.5	9.8	49.0	44.8
5	2.0	10.9	54.5	49.9
6	2.5	11.7	58.5	53.5
7	4.0	11.9	59.5	54.4
8	5.0	12.3	61.5	56.3
9	7.5	12.7	63.5	58.1
10	10.0	13.4	67.0	61.3
11	12.5	13.7	68.5	62.7

Table-5.7 CBR Test Data with Geogrid @3H/4 from bottom

CBR @ 2.5 mm Penetration :3.91, CBR @ 5.0 mm Penetration :1.80

Description	CBR Value
Without geogrid	1.67
With geogrid @ H/4 from the bottom	1.80
With geogrid @H/2 from the bottom	2.50
With geogrid @ 3H/4 from the bottom	3.91

Table -6 CBR Value Variation with Geogrid Application in Soil Sample

CHAPTER-6

DESIGN OF PAVEMENT as per (IRC: 37-2012)

Bituminous Surfacing with Granular Base and Granular Sub-base

Fig-6.1 Bituminous Surfacing with GB and GSB

IRC: 37-2012

Graph-6.1 Plate-2 (IRC:37-2012) Pavement Design Catalogues

WITHOUT GEOGRID: CBR: 1.67 %, N: 47.45 msa ≈ 50 msa

i.e., not fit for laying a road directly on the Subgrade soil; which needs Stabilization to it.

WITH GEOGRID AT 3H/4 FROM BOTTOM: CBR: 3.91 %, N: 47.45 msa ≈ 50 msa

i.e., the thickness of GSB: 300 mm, G. Base:250, DBM: 115 mm, BC/SDBC:40mm

Where; **GSB**: Granular Sub-base, **G. Base**: Granular Base, **DBM**: Dense Bituminous Macadam, **BC**: Bituminous Concrete, **SDBC**: Semi-Dense Bituminous Concrete.

The thickness of pavement required in MM:

Thickness	Without grid	With Geogrid @ H/4 from bottom
GSB	NA	300
G.BASE	NA	250
DBM	NA	115
BC	NA	40
Total	NA	705

Table-6.1 Thickness of Pavement in mm contrast with the application of geogrid

CHAPTER-7

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The positive effects of geogrid reinforced subgrade courses can economically and ecologically be utilized to reduce aggregate thickness. And it can also increase the life of the pavement and can also decrease the overall cost of the pavement construction with an increased lifetime.

The study investigated the application of geogrids to subgrade material as a form of reinforcement to road construction. The inclusion of the geo-grid considerably increases the strength of poor soils, which is reflected in the higher CBR values. The study shows that the strength of the subgrade is significantly altered positively by the positioning of the geo-grid at varying depth. It was observed that the highest subgrade strength is achieved when it is placed at $3H/4$ for a single layer although has a satisfactory result at $H/2$ and $H/4$ respectively. On reinforcing the soil, there is a considerable increase in performance of the subgrade in the unsoaked condition. The use of geogrids as reinforcement to poor soils improves its strength. It is non-bio degradable and therefore durable; it also increases the ultimate service life of the pavement. The use of Geogrids should, therefore, be encouraged as an effective and modern form of improving road construction on poor sub-grade materials. Further research should be analyzed in ascertaining the effect of geogrids on subgrade soils under the unsoaked condition

FUTURE SCOPE

From above discussion, it can be said that geogrids may serve better even on soaked conditions too. We have collected traffic data only for two-lane two-way traffic. It can be applicable to more lanes also. It can be applicable for plain, rolling, hilly and steep roads also. For any industrial region where the traffic is high, it is suggested to place more than a single layer of geogrid.

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